

URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS IN PREGNANCY: TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT

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Annotation. According to the literature, the incidence of gestational pyelonephritis (GP) is 5-10%, while the development of the disease increases the risk of intrauterine infection and miscarriage (Styazhkina S.N. et al., 2015). The study of the interaction between gestational pyelonephritis and pregnancy is relevant due to the high percentage of obstetric complications, negative perinatal outcomes and severe diseases in newborns, which emphasizes the medical and socio-economic significance of the problem. In chronic pyelonephritis, pregnancy is complicated by iron deficiency anemia (35-70%), premature termination of pregnancy at various stages (15-20%), chronic placental insufficiency (30-35%), preeclampsia (35-70%). 30-40% causes complications such as chronic uterine hypoxia (30-40%), fetal infection (20-30%) and growth retardation (12-15%). In chronic pyelonephritis, the ability of pregnant women to adapt to newborns is significantly impaired and the risk of early neonatal death increases.

Keywords: gestational pyelonephritis, pregnancy, treatment, childbirth.

The aim of the research: is to study the effect of GP on the course and outcome of pregnancy.

Material and methods. We observed 72 pregnant women who received treatment for GP in the pregnancy pathology department of the Samarkand State medical university clinic in the period 2023-2024.

The distribution of patients was as follows: 12-22 weeks - 25 (34.8%), 23-31 weeks - 12 (22.4%), 32-38 weeks - 35 (47.8%). Among the clinical symptoms in combination of pregnancy and GP, the following prevailed: pain syndrome in the lumbar region on the right (55.6%; n = 40), febrile body temperature (17.4%; n = 12), subfebrile temperature (27.8%; n = 20), dysuria (16.7%; n = 12). According to the results of laboratory tests, leukocyturia was detected in 42 pregnant women (58.4%), erythrocyturia - in 21 (29.1%), proteinuria - in 39 (54.1%), bacteriuria - in 14 (19.4%). Leukocytosis was noted in 13 (18%), and an increase in ESR in 23 (32%). In all cases, treatment was carried out aimed at relieving the symptoms of GP, with antispasmodic drugs used in 100%, and antibacterial drugs - only in 14 patients (19.4%). Further observation of pregnant women revealed the following complications of gestation: threatened miscarriage (TM) was diagnosed in 52 (72.4%), anemia - in 30 (41.6%), fetoplacental insufficiency (FPI) - in 7 (9%), chronic fetal hypoxia - in 6 (8%), preeclampsia (PE) - in 4 (5%). In addition, recurrence of GP was observed in 26% of cases. Premature birth (PL) at 23-32 weeks was recorded in 7 women (9.7%).

Conclusion. Thus, according to our data, GP often develops at gestation periods of 32-38 weeks, is accompanied by an erased clinical picture, and negatively affects the further course of pregnancy, increasing the risk of FPI, PE and TM.

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